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Impact of composition changes of alumina rich slags on the corrosion of refractories found in steel ladles

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Refractories are used in steel making equipment thanks to their properties. In steel ladles a corrosive layer of slag floats on top of the steel. It helps protect and treat it but it degrades the lining due to corrosion. This corrosion leads to changes in the microstructure and properties which decrease their performances.

Nowadays, to modify or improve the grade of steel, processes change. One way to do it is adjusting the composition of slags. However, this leads to changes in corrosion mechanisms. To predict how it affect refractories microstructures, several corrosion tests using refractory bricks (MgO-C and alumina-spinel) and alumina rich synthetic slags with different compositions were conducted. First, the raw materials used in the bricks were mixed with the different slags to determine the reactions than can take place. Then contact test and rotating finger test with bricks and slags were done to see how the different reactions combine inside the bricks.

Samples were mainly analysed by XRD and SEM. It appeared that the changes of slag composition can have opposite effect on the raw materials and that it modifies the rates and the importance of the corrosion of the bricks.

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